

CODEN [USA]: IAJPB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR
SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF ACECLOFENAC AND
PREGABALIN IN BULK DRUG AND PHARMACEUTICAL
DOSAGE FORM****P. Pravalika*, R Rani, T.Rama Rao**

Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis, CMR College of Pharmacy, Hyderabad, Telangana

Abstract:

A simple, precise, accurate and robust UV Spectroscopic method has been developed for the simultaneous estimation of Aceclofenac and Pregabalin in bulk and tablet dosage forms. In this process the Simultaneous Estimation of the Aceclofenac and Pregabalin was carried out by the simultaneous equation method using Methanol as solvent with 275 nm and 210 nm i.e., λ_{max} of Aceclofenac and Pregabalin respectively. The linearity observed for Aceclofenac was in the range of 2-10 μ g/ml and for Pregabalin was in the range of 2-10 μ g/ml. The %RSD for precision for both drugs was <2. The accuracy of methods was assessed by recovery studies and the % recovery was found to be within the range of 98.8-99.72 and 99.3-99.7% for both Aceclofenac and Pregabalin respectively. The developed method was validated with respect to linearity, accuracy (recovery), and precision. LOD and LOQ for Aceclofenac was found to be 0.210 μ g/ml and 0.638 μ g/ml and LOD and LOQ for Pregabalin was found to be 0.1778 μ g/ml and 0.5388 μ g/ml respectively. The % Assay was found to be 99.86 and 98.8 for Aceclofenac and Pregabalin respectively. The method was validated as per ICH guidelines and can be employed for simultaneous estimation of both drugs in pharmaceutical formulations with no interference from any other excipients.

Keywords: Aceclofenac and Pregabalin, UV-spectroscopy, Methanol.

Corresponding author:***P. Pravalika,**

Address: CMR College of Pharmacy,
Hyderabad, Telangana, PIN-501401

Mobile No. 9963100541

Email: pravalika.jntu@gmail.com.

QR code

Please cite this article in press P. Pravalika et al., *Method Development And Validation For Simultaneous Estimation Of Aceclofenac And Pregabalin In Bulk Drug And Pharmaceutical Dosage Form.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2024; 11 (12).

INTRODUCTION:

Aceclofenac is an NSAID, used in the management of osteoarthritis, rheumatoid arthritis and ankylosing spondylitis. Its IUPAC name is 2-(2-(2-(2,6-dichlorophenyl) amino) phenyl acetyl) oxy acetic acid. It inhibits cyclooxygenase (COX)-1 and-2 which are the enzyme responsible for producing prostaglandins (PGs). PGs contribute to inflammation and pain signalling⁽¹⁻²⁾. The literature survey revealed that few analytical methods have been published concerning the simultaneous estimation of Aceclofenac and Pregabalin⁽³⁻⁴⁾. Pregabalin is official in Indian pharmacopoeia and its IUPAC name is s-3-amino methyl 5-methyl hexanoic acid. Aceclofenac is used in various pain conditions like rheumatoid arthritis, osteoarthritis and ankylosing spondylitis. Pregabalin is a new anticonvulsant and analgesic medication that was recently approved for adjunctive treatment of partial seizures in adults in both the United States and Europe and for treatment of neuropathic pain from postherpetic neuralgia and diabetic neuropathy⁽⁵⁻⁶⁾. The aim of the present work is to develop a simple, precise, accurate and robust UV Spectroscopic method has been developed for the simultaneous estimation of Aceclofenac and Pregabalin in bulk and tablet dosage forms and validate it as per ICH guidelines⁽⁷⁻⁹⁾.

Fig 1 Structure of Aceclofenac

Fig 2 Structure of Pregabalin

MATERIALS AND METHODS:**Instruments:**

UV-visible spectrophotometer with UV Win software (PG Instrument) and matching quartz cells with a 1 cm cell path length with wavelength accuracy of 0.1 nm and Weighing balance.

Chemicals:

Aceclofenac (API) and Pregabalin (API) pure were procured from local suppliers. The marketed combination pharmaceutical dosage form of Aceclofenac tablets (200mg) and Pregabalin tablets (75mg) was purchased from local pharmacy and Methanol from Merck labs.

Solvent selection:

After many trails both the drugs were solubilize in, methanol. Finally, methanol was selected as a solvent.

METHODOLOGY:

Preparation of Aceclofenac standard stock solution: Standard stock solution was prepared by accurately weighing 10mg of Aceclofenac and transferred in to 10ml of volumetric flask and then dissolved in few ml of methanol until it solubilizes and the volume was made up to the mark with methanol to obtain the concentration of 1mg/ml or 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (standard stock solution-1). From stock 1 solution pipette out 1 ml and transfer to 10 ml volumetric flask and made up to the mark with methanol, to obtain the concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (standard stock solution-2).

Preparation of Pregabalin standard stock solution:

Standard stock solution was prepared by accurately weighing 10mg of Pregabalin and transferred in to 10ml of volumetric flask and then dissolved in few ml of methanol until it solubilizes and the volume was made up to the mark with methanol to obtain the concentration of 1mg/ml or 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (standard stock solution-1). From stock 1 solution pipette out 1 ml and transfer to 10 ml volumetric flask and made up to the mark with methanol, to obtain the concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (standard stock solution 2)

Selection of λ_{max} for analysis of Aceclofenac and Pregabalin:

Individual 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ solutions of Aceclofenac and Pregabalin was used for initial spectral scan in the UV range of 200-400 nm to give λ_{max} of 275 nm and 210 nm respectively.

Preparation of serial dilutions:

The serial dilutions were prepared from the standard stock-2 solutions of Aceclofenac and Pregabalin to get a respective concentration of 2µg/mL, 4µg/mL, 6µg/mL, 8µg/mL, & 10µg/mL and absorbance of both drug solutions was measured at λ_{max} of 275 nm for Aceclofenac and 210 for Pregabalin respectively.

Linearity:

Calibration curve was plotted by taking absorbance on x-axis and concentration on y-axis

ASSAY:

A combination marketed tablet of brand name ZERODOL PG 200/75 was used for assay. Taken 10 tablets were accurately weighed, and average weight was calculated, they were crushed to fine powder. The weight of powder equivalent to 100 mg Aceclofenac and Pregabalin was dissolved in methanol with the help of sonication and volume was made up using methanol up to the mark of 100 ml volumetric flask gives the concentration of 1000 µg/ml. The stock solution was filtered by using Whatman filter paper and the solution was further dilute with methanol to give 6 µg/ml. Measure the absorbance of the solution at 275 nm and at 210nm. The concentration of two drugs in sample were determined by using simultaneous equation method.

$$CX = \frac{A1 \times ay2 - A2 \times ay1}{ax2 ay2 - ax1 ay2}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:**Determination of λ_{max} for analysis of Aceclofenac and Pregabalin:**

Individual 10µg/ml solutions of Aceclofenac and Pregabalin was used for initial spectral scan in the UV range of 200-400 nm to give λ_{max} of 275 nm and 210 nm respectively shown in Figure 3

Figure 3: Absorption spectrum of Aceclofenac

Figure 4: Absorption spectrum of Pregabalin

Linearity:

The linearity concentration for Aceclofenac and Pregabalin in the range of 2-10 μ g/ml. The linearity data was shown in Table 1 and 2 and calibration curve was shown in Figure 5 and 6. The correlation coefficient, intercept and slope were calculated for Aceclofenac and Pregabalin results were shown in Table 3.

Table 1: Linearity data of Aceclofenac

S.No.	Concentration(μ g/ml)	Absorbance
1	2	0.105
2	4	0.199
3	6	0.289
4	8	0.373
5	10	0.466

Table 2: Linearity data of Pregabalin

S.No.	Concentration(μ g/ml)	Absorbance
1	2	0.171
2	4	0.354
3	6	0.552
4	8	0.709
5	10	0.914

Figure 6: Calibration curve of pregabalin at 210nm

Table 3: Optical characteristics of Aceclofenac and Pregabalin

Parameters	Aceclofenac	Pregabalin
λ max	275nm	210nm
Slope	0.0460	0.0911
Linearity	2 to 10 μ g/ml	2 to 10 μ g/ml
Correlation coefficient	0.999	0.999
Intercept	0.0083	0.0059

Discussion: Calibration curve was plotted and correlation coefficient was found to be 0.999. So, there was a good correlation between absorbance and concentration.

Assay: Results of estimation of Aceclofenac and Pregabalin in Formulation. Table 4.

Table 4: Assay of Marketed Formulation

Drug	Label claim(mg)	%Assay \pm S. D
Aceclofenac	200	99.86 \pm 0.025
Pregabalin	75	98.72 \pm 0.030

Discussion: The % Assay of Aceclofenac and Pregabalin was found to be 99.86 and 98.72% respectively. It shows that UV Spectroscopic method developed was successful in determining Aceclofenac and Pregabalin from tablet dosage form.

Precision: Intraday precision of Aceclofenac and Pregabalin data was shown in Table 5 and Interday precision of Aceclofenac and Pregabalin data was shown in Table 6 and 7 respectively.

Table 5: Intraday Precision data of Aceclofenac and Pregabalin

Concentration (μ g/ml)	Aceclofenac	Pregabalin
6	0.285	0.552
6	0.289	0.553
6	0.285	0.554
6	0.285	0.553
6	0.284	0.552
6	0.287	0.553
MEAN	0.2858	0.552833
STDEV	0.001835	0.000753
%RSD	0.62	0.13

Table 6: Inter day Precision data of Aceclofenac

Concentration (μ g/ml)	DAY-1	DAY-2
6	0.285	0.279
6	0.289	0.278
6	0.285	0.276
6	0.285	0.278
6	0.284	0.276
6	0.287	0.278
MEAN	0.2858	0.2771
STDEV	0.001835	0.00133
%RSD	0.62	0.469

Table 7: Interday Precision data of Pregabalin

Concentration (µg/ml)	DAY-1	DAY-2
6	0.552	0.552
6	0.553	0.552
6	0.554	0.554
6	0.553	0.553
6	0.552	0.551
6	0.553	0.553
MEAN	0.552833	0.5525
STDEV	0.000753	0.00104
%RSD	0.13	0.18

Discussion: The %RSD for intraday and interday precision of the Aceclofenac and Pregabalin was found to be <2%. It indicates that the method was precise.

Limit of detection and Limit of quantification: LOD and LOQ was calculated and shown in Table 8.

Table 8: LOD and LOQ data

PARAMETERS	Aceclofenac (µg/ml)	Pregabalin (µg/ml)
LOD	0.210	0.177
LOQ	0.638	0.538

Discussion: LOD and LOQ values for Aceclofenac and Pregabalin was found to be 0.210 µg/mL and 0.638 µg/ml. 0.1778µg/ml and 0.5388µg/ml. It indicates that the method was sensitive.

Accuracy:

Recovery studies: Recovery studies were carried out for Aceclofenac and Pregabalin was shown in Table 9 and 10 respectively.

Table 9: Accuracy data of Aceclofenac:

(% level)	Amount Taken(µg/ml)	Amount Recovered (µg/ml)	% Recovery	Average
80	4.8	4.79	99.9	99.63
	4.8	4.77	99.5	
	4.8	4.77	99.5	
100	6	6.015	100.2	99.72
	6	5.993	99.8	
	6	5.95	99.16	
120	7.2	7.12	98.8	98.83
	7.2	7.097	98.5	
	7.2	7.145	99.2	

Table 10: Accuracy data of Pregabalin

(% level)	Amount Taken($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Amount Recovered ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	% Recovery	Average
80	4.8	4.75	99.8	99.33
	4.8	4.74	98.7	
	4.8	4.78	99.5	
120	7.2	7.16	99.4	99.36
	7.2	7.13	99.1	
	7.2	7.17	99.6	
100	6	5.97	99.6	99.73
	6	5.98	99.7	
	6	5.99	99.9	

Discussion: The average % recovery of Aceclofenac and Pregabalin was found to be in the range of 98-102% respectively.

Robustness: Robustness for the Aceclofenac and Pregabalin data was shown in Table 11 and 12 respectively.

Table 11: Robustness data of Aceclofenac

S. No.	WAVE LENGTH	ABSORBANCE
1	277	0.541
2	275	0.550
3	273	0.542

Table 12: Robustness data of Pregabalin

S.No.	WAVELENGTH	ABSORBANCE
1	212	0.59
2	210	0.55
3	208	0.60

Discussion: There was no much variation in the absorbance with change in λ_{max} .

CONCLUSION:

From the above experimental results and parameters, it was concluded that, this developed UV Spectroscopy method for simultaneous estimation of Aceclofenac and Pregabalin was found to be simple, precise, accurate, robust, and rapid makes this method more acceptable and cost effective and it can be effectively applied for routine analysis in research institutions and in quality control department.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We are thankful to CMR College of Pharmacy management and principal for providing facilities and equipment for carrying out the work.

REFERENCES:

1. A Bose, PP Dash, MK Sahoo, Simple Spectrophotometric methods for estimation of

Aceclofenac from bulk and formulations, National Library of Medicine.2010;1(1):57-60.

- Hitendra kumar, Gelani, Payal, Samir, Practical Implication of Chromatographic and Pregabalin in bulk and Pharmaceutical Dosage forms. Chromatography research International.2014;1-5.
- B.M. Gurupadayya, Suchithra TJ, Simultaneous Estimation of Aceclofenac and Pregabalin in Combined Dosage form by solubility-based separation method. Acta Scientific Pharmaceutical Sciences.2018;2(12):20-26.
- Mayur T. Narkhede, Sachin S. Rane, Rajesh Y, Chaudhari, Vijay R. Patil, Development and validation of UV Spectrophotometric method for the Simultaneous Estimation of Aceclofenac and Pregabalin in bulk drugs and Pharmaceutical Dosage form, World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.2021;2062-2072.

5. S.D. Jadhav, V. S. Madankar, Chaudhari, Analytical method development and validation of Aceclofenac in bulk and Marketed formulation, Journal of Emerging technologies and Innovative Research.2018;5(5):428-437.
6. Rajinder Singh Gujral, SK Manirul Haque, Prem shanker, Development and validation of Pregabalin in bulk pharmaceutical formulations and in human urine samples by UV Spectrophotometry, International Journal of Biomedical Science, issue 5(2):175-180, 2009.
7. Pravalika P, Namami Dutt, Likitha K, Spectrophotometric method for the determination of Dorzolamide in bulk drug and pharmaceutical dosage form. IJRTI, 2017, 4, 7(8), 1193-1197.
8. Federal Register, vol 60. IFPMA, Switzerland, Draft ICH Guidelines on Validation of Analytical Procedures Definitions and terminology, 1995, pp.1126.
9. Geneva, Switzerland, ICH Harmonized Tripartite Guidelines, Code Q2B, Validation of Analytical Procedures; Methodology, 1996.
10. ICH Q2A, Validation of analytical methods, definitions and terminology, ICH Harmonized tripartite guideline, 1999.